

Modeling and simulation of ammonia jets under flash boiling conditions

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Abstract

This study examines the flash boiling of liquid ammonia in a step-counterbore nozzle using both equilibrium and non-equilibrium thermodynamic models. A comparative analysis is conducted between the Homogeneous Relaxation Model (HRM) and the Real Fluid Model (RFM) to evaluate their effectiveness in predicting key spray characteristics. The study investigates the influence of thermodynamic assumptions on spray behavior, focusing on key parameters such as vaporization rate, density, velocity, temperature distribution and spray cone angle. The impact of liquid metastability on flash boiling atomization is explored by comparing the non-equilibrium HRM modeling with the equilibrium RFM framework. It has been shown that flare flash boiling inside the nozzle can affect the spray behavior and its cone angle. The numerical predictions are assessed against experimental data to determine the strengths and limitations of each model in capturing flash boiling dynamics.

Keywords: Flash Boiling, Ammonia Spray, Real Fluid Model (RFM), Homogeneous Relaxation Model (HRM), CONVERGE CFD

Introduction

The global pursuit of net zero carbon emissions has intensified interest in alternative fuels, and ammonia is emerging as a promising candidate due to its high energy density, well-established production infrastructure and relatively safer storage and transport properties. However, a major drawback of ammonia as a fuel is its poor combustion properties, such as low flammability and low flame speed. A blend of ammonia with highly flammable fuels has been found to help overcome these limitations. Further, the use of liquid ammonia has several advantageous: avoid an additional vaporization system and decrease the local temperature and therefore thermal NO_x formation [1, 2]. In combustion applications, achieving fine fuel droplets through atomization is crucial for enhancing efficiency [3]. Flash boiling has long been recognized as an effective method for atomizing conventional fuels, improving fuel-air mixing and combustion performance. Ammonia, with its low boiling point, undergoes flash atomization naturally, making it advantageous for producing fine droplets and enhancing atomization efficiency. Recent studies [4, 5] have explored this potential, extending flash boiling applications to unconventional fuels like ammonia. Flash boiling occurs when a liquid undergoes rapid phase change due to a sudden pressure drop below its saturation pressure, leading to explosive vaporization and enhanced atomization. The onset of flash boiling is characterized by the non-dimensional number R_p , where R_p is defined as the ratio of saturation pressure at fluid temperature ($P_{sat}(T_f)$) to ambient pressure (P_{amb}), i.e., $R_p = \frac{P_{sat}(T_f)}{P_{amb}}$. Flash boiling occurs when $R_p > 1$, indicating that the fluid temperature exceeds the saturation threshold for the given ambient pressure, triggering intense vaporization. Over the past few years, experimental studies have explored the flash boiling behavior of ammonia and other non-conventional fuels under various injection conditions. Okafor et al. [6] analyzed the effects of injection pressure and temperature on ammonia jet breakup, revealing that increasing superheat leads to a more rapid transition from liquid jets to vapor-dominated plumes. Li et al. [7] investigated the near-field and far-field characteristics of superheated ammonia spray. They found that both superheat degree and fuel viscosity play significant roles in the entire flashing region. Tang et al. [8] examined the spray macroscopic and microscopic characteristics at non-flash, transition flash, and flare flash boiling regions with a single-hole injector.

They observed that the spray significantly expands in the radial direction at flare flash boiling regions ($R_p \leq 0.47$), while the spray contracts in the penetration direction at the transition flash boiling region ($0.47 < R_p \leq 1.06$). Fan et al. [9] compared the spray characteristics of liquid ammonia and ethanol in a pressure swirl atomizer. Furthermore, studies by Shchigel et al. [10] highlighted the impact of nozzle geometry and injection pressure on the atomization process, showing that narrow nozzles enhance secondary breakup due to increased shear forces. In addition, Toshinaga et al. [11] examined ammonia-mixed fuel sprays, concluding that the mixing of ammonia with hydrogen or other fuels can modify the vaporization characteristics and improve the combustion stability. Zhang et al. [12] investigated the performance of a two-stroke, low-speed engine utilizing an ammonia/diesel dual direct injection strategy. They showed by tuning the injection timings of both diesel and ammonia, a reduction in fuel-based NO_x emissions can be achieved. Pelé et al. [13] studied the spray characteristics of ammonia, biofuel, ethanol, and gasoline with a typical GDI injector. Colson et al. [14] studied the effect of flow temperature and nozzle geometry near to the flash transition regime. Scharl et al. [15] presented a 1-D model to predict the spray penetration length. Caradona and Guiberti [16] investigated the effect of injection pressure, air flow, and flow temperature of liquid ammonia in a twin-fluid atomizer. Despite these advancements, experimental challenges persist in measuring droplet size distributions, differentiating fuel and vapor mass fraction, and quantifying phase transition kinetics. Thus, computational modeling turns out to be an essential tool for the flash boiling modeling.

A number of phenomena happens simultaneously during flash boiling, from molecular scale to macroscale. Modeling every phenomenon extensively is quite challenging. Nevertheless, various numerical approaches exist, knowing the advantages and limitation of the methods thus become important. The Eulerian-Lagrangian approach, coupled with evaporation and nucleation models, being the most widely employed in the spray modeling community. Sazhin [17] reviewed various evaporation models and their ability to model conventional fuels. Raju et al. [18] presented a superheat vaporization model as an improvement to previous evaporation models. Kumar [19] explored how nozzle exit conditions and droplet initialization influence the accuracy of Lagrangian-Eulerian simulations for flashing sprays. Shin and Park [20] presented a new secondary breakup model based on energy and force analysis for liquid ammonia. Kurose et al. [21] investigated various evaporation models for modeling liquid ammonia spray. They suggested a combined Zuo and Langmuir-Knudsen model for flash boiling conditions. Huang et al. [22,23] did a sensitivity analysis for various parameters in spray evaporation for liquid ammonia atomization. Somarthane et al. [24,25] performed 3D LES simulations to study the combustion properties of liquid ammonia. Zembi et al. [26] reported that each flashing regime needs a calibration independently for the spray models.

The process of flashing is an in-nozzle or near the nozzle exit phenomenon. Thus, Eulerian-Eulerian approach is more suitable in order to understand this phenomenon. Indeed, this approach can help to obtain an overall result from all the processes involved in in-nozzle flash boiling and near-nozzle atomization, and need not to have a separate modeling for each phenomenon like nucleation, evaporation, and bubble growth induced atomization, etc. The Homogenous Relaxation Model (HRM) is the most widely used Eulerian-Eulerian model for the simulation of flash-boiling. This model takes into account the non-equilibrium evaporation and metastable liquid states. In addition, the phases have the same pressure and temperature, but are allowed to have different chemical potential. The HRM model, as formulated by Downar-Zapolski et al. [27], requires a relaxation time to account for time delay in the phase transition. A relaxation-time correlation developed for water by Downar-Zapolski et al. [27] is usually calibrated for predicting the vaporization rate of superheated liquid jets. Guo and Torelli [28] proposed a modified model to account for the effect of fuel-air mixing at vapor-liquid equilibrium. Rachakonda et al. [29] coupled the flow solver with a surface area density model to accurately predict the spray plume under flashing conditions. Guo et al. [30] did a parametric study for a flashing jet of n-Hexane using HRM and showed a good comparison for wide range of temperature and pressure. Gartner et al. [31] studied the spray collapse phenomenon in a GDI injector using the Eulerian-Eulerian methodology. Saha et al. [32] presented a combined Eulerian-Lagrangian approach under flash boiling conditions for a GDI injector. Wang et al. [33] investigated liquid ammonia spray under wide degree of superheat and nozzle aspect ratio using HRM. Kumar and Dam [34] investigated liquid ammonia flash boiling using Eulerian-Lagrangian coupled approach similar to Saha et al. [32].

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in achieving high-fidelity simulations, particularly in capturing metastability in non-equilibrium phase transitions, vaporization cooling effects, and heterogeneous nucleation at walls. Existing computational models are heavily dependent on the tuning of the model parameters for various flashing regimes, but also for sub-cooled conditions. Because, the thermodynamic modelling plays a crucial role in phase transition phenomenon, a real-fluid modeling (RFM) framework has been developed at IFPEN [35–40]. In the RFM framework, the required thermodynamic and transport properties are computed using the in-house thermodynamic library Carnot [41] and stored

in a lookup-table which is used during multidimensional simulations runtime. Particularly, this RFM methodology along-with sub-grid scale surface area density model has been used previously [42] with conventional hydrocarbon fuels and has proven its appropriateness in predicting high pressure Diesel sprays in transcritical conditions.

This paper studies the application of two different models using equilibrium and non-equilibrium thermodynamics to simulate the flash boiling of ammonia (NH₃) in a typical step-counterbore nozzle. A comparative analysis is conducted between the Homogeneous Relaxation Model (HRM) and the Real Fluid Model (RFM) to evaluate their effectiveness in predicting key spray characteristics. The next section describes the RFM and HRM model used in the present work. The result and discussion section describes the case setup, and systematic study to investigate the influence of thermodynamic assumptions on spray behavior, focusing on parameters such as spray cone angle, vaporization effects, density, velocity and temperature distribution. Additionally, the impact of surface attachment, nucleation site effects, and metastable region thermodynamics on flash boiling atomization is explored.

1 Solver Description

For the the Real Fluid (RFM) Model [42], a fully compressible two-phase flow solver under the assumption of mechanical and thermal equilibrium is used, i.e. the two phases have the same velocity, pressure and temperature. Thus, the governing equations are a four-equation model given as,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_i u_j}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\tau_{ij} + \tau_{ij}^{SGS}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho e}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho e u_j}{\partial x_j} = -P \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j} + (\tau_{ij} + \tau_{ij}^{SGS}) \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (q_j + q_j^{SGS}) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho Y_k}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho Y_k u_j}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (J_{kj} + J_{kj}^{SGS}) \quad (4)$$

where ρ, u, P, T, e are the Favre-filtered mixture density, velocity, Pressure and specific internal energy respectively. The viscous stress tensor is calculated as $\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} \right)$. Here, u_i is the velocity in the direction of x_i and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker-delta. The heat flux and species diffusion flux are defined as $q_j = -\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + \sum_m J_{mj} h_m$ and $J_{mj} = -\rho D_m \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial x_j}$, respectively. Here, the subscript m represents the species. The fluid properties like thermal diffusivity λ and dynamic viscosity μ are computed by Chung et al. [43] correlations. D_m is the molecular diffusivity constant, Y_m is the mass-fraction, and h_m is the specific enthalpy for the species m . The sub-grid stress tensor (τ_{ij}^{SGS}) is computed by replacing the molecular dynamic μ by μ_{SGS} , i.e., $\tau_{ij}^{SGS} = \frac{\mu_{SGS}}{\mu} \tau_{ij}$. The sub-grid scale species and heat fluxes are modelled using the turbulent transport properties as $q_j^{SGS} = -\lambda_t \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + \sum_m J_{mj}^{SGS} h_m$ and $J_{mj}^{SGS} = -\rho D_{mt} \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial x_j}$. The turbulent transport properties are modeled by using turbulent Schmidt number $Sc_t = 0.7$ and turbulent Prandtl number $Pr_t = 0.9$ as $D_{mt} = \frac{\mu_{SGS}}{\rho Sc_t}$, $\lambda_t = \frac{C_p \mu_{SGS}}{Pr_t}$. C_p is the isobaric heat capacity. The sub-grid scale eddy viscosity μ_{SGS} is modeled by the sigma model [44] as $\mu_{SGS} = \rho (C \Delta)^2 \delta$, where $C = 1.5$ is the model constant, $\Delta = V^{-1/3}$, and $\delta = \frac{\sigma_3(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)(\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)}{\sigma_1^2}$. Here, V is the cell volume, δ is the differential operator, and σ_i are the singular values of the resolved velocity gradient tensor. It should be noted that the Soret and Dufour effects are neglected in the present model and left for consideration in future studies.

1.1 Homogeneous Relaxation Model (HRM)

In HRM [27], a source term is added to the species equation (Equation 4), as explained in [45]. HRM predicts the mass exchange between liquid and vapor by describing the rate at which the quality of the vapor $X = \frac{m_{vap}}{m_{vap} + m_{liq}}$ will reach its thermodynamic equilibrium value \bar{X} . Here, m_{vap}, m_{liq} are the mass of vapor and liquid phase in a cell. The non-equilibrium effect is modeled through a first-order rate equation.

$$\frac{DX}{Dt} = \frac{\bar{X} - X}{\theta} \quad (5)$$

Where, θ is the characteristic time scale of the phase change process to attain the equilibrium. Smaller value of θ implies faster phase-change and a near equilibrium state. For single-component phase change, θ is modeled as $\theta = \theta_0 \alpha^{-0.54} \psi^{-1.76}$, where void fraction $\alpha = \frac{Y_v}{\rho_v} \left(\frac{Y_v}{\rho_v} + \frac{Y_l}{\rho_l} \right)^{-1}$ and pressure fraction $\psi = \frac{P_{sat} - P}{P_c - P_{sat}}$. θ_0 is the empirical constant taken as 3.96×10^{-7} , Y_v, Y_l are the species mass-fraction, ρ_v, ρ_l are the density of the vapor and liquid phase, P_{sat} is the saturation pressure, and P_c is the critical pressure. The source term that is added to Equation 4 is given as

$$S = \frac{X^1 - X^0}{V \Delta t} (m_{vap} + m_{liq}) \quad (6)$$

1.2 Real Fluid Model (RFM)

In the present RFM, a uniformly discretized thermodynamic table for binary systems has been generated using the IFPEN-Carnot thermodynamic library [41]. This library employs a robust isothermal-isobaric (TP) flash using the Peng-Robinson equation of state [46] to perform Vapor Liquid Equilibrium (VLE) calculations. The tabular input data is indexed by temperature, pressure, and species mass fraction. The generated look-up table includes equilibrium mixture density, internal energy, and key thermodynamic properties such as the vapor fraction, heat capacity, speed of sound, and transport properties. The tabulated data are interpolated using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) method [47] during simulations. This approach, applicable to binary [35] and ternary [48] mixtures, is integrated into the CONVERGE CFD solver [45] as detailed in [35, 36, 40]. The thermodynamic table is utilized during simulations for:

- Properties lookup as a function $f(T, P, Y_k)$.
- Temperature reverse lookup: Updating temperature after solving the internal energy equation as a function $T = f(e, P, Y_k)$.

2 Results and Discussion

The aim of this work is to compare the above numerical models for the injection of ammonia in the flash boiling regime. The operating conditions of liquid ammonia injection are listed in Table 1. They correspond to a flare flash boiling regime with a relatively high superheat index, $R_p = 10$. A 0.05% of dissolved nitrogen mass fraction in ammonia is also assumed at injection, as experimentally liquid ammonia is pressurized by nitrogen.

Table 1. Working conditions of liquid ammonia injection

Parameter	Value
Fuel	Liquid NH_3 (0.05% Dissolved N_2 mass fraction)
Injection Pressure P_{inj}	70 bar
Injection Temperature T_f	298 K
Chamber Pressure P_{amb} T_f	1 bar
Superheat index R_p	10 bar

2.1 Numerical Setup

The computational domain consists of an injection nozzle (called SPRAY-MSH) with a hole diameter of $d = 0.17$ mm and a counter-bore step diameter of $D = 0.4$ mm, and a cylindrical chamber with dimensions $L = 350D$ and $R = 58D$. The base grid has a cell size of $\Delta = 544 \mu m$, with fixed embedding applied inside the nozzle and near the nozzle exit. A six-level embedding refinement is used, resulting in a minimum cell size of $\Delta = 8.5 \mu m$. The total mesh contains approximately 6.1 million cells. The mesh structure is illustrated in Figure 1. Region 0 and Region 1 are initialized with liquid ammonia NH_3 with 0.05% dissolved N_2 mass fraction. Region 2-4 were given ambient conditions. Pressure profile is chosen at the inlet to match the experimental mass-flow rate. The key details of the numerical setup are mentioned in Table 2.

2.2 Comparison of HRM and RFM

In this section, we compare the results of the Homogeneous Relaxation Model (HRM) and the real fluid model (RFM) for the spray of liquid ammonia under flash boiling conditions, $R_p = 10$. Both models aim to capture the complex phase change dynamics, but they differ in their fundamental approach to

Figure 1. (a) Cross-Sectional view of the mesh where $\Delta = 544\mu\text{m}$, $\Delta_1 = 34\mu\text{m}$, $\Delta_2 = 8.5\mu\text{m}$. (b) Zoomed view near nozzle exit.

Table 2. Numerics details of the setup

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	
INLET	Pressure – Dirichlet (Total Pressure = User-Defined profile) Temperature – Dirichlet ($T = T_f$)
NOZZLE WALLS	Velocity - No-Slip Temperature – Dirichlet ($T = T_f$)
OUTLET	Pressure – Dirichlet (Ambient) Temperature – Dirichlet (Ambient)
NUMERICAL SCHEMES	
SPATIAL	2^{nd} Order
TEMPORAL	2^{nd} Order for momentum equation and 1^{st} Order for the rest.
THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES	
HRM	Peng-Robinson (EoS) for gas and a barotropic EoS for the liquid.
RFM	Peng-Robinson (EoS) for gas and TP-Flash VLE Tabulated Properties for liquid and vapor
CFL CONDITION	1.0

handling phase change and non-equilibrium effects. HRM models the phase transition using a relaxation timescale, while RFM incorporates a detailed equilibrium thermodynamic framework based on real fluid properties. By analyzing key parameters such as density and temperature distribution, vapor mass fraction, and the initial in-nozzle atomization and spray behavior, the strengths and limitations of each model in predicting flash-boiling behavior are discussed.

Figure 2 illustrates the density distribution near the nozzle exit, highlighting the contrasting spray behaviors predicted by the RFM and HRM models. In RFM, flash-boiling eats away the liquid-gas interface and throws the torn ligaments against the wall of the counter-bore step. In fact, the liquid sprayed by the flash-boiling impacts the step-walls and slides towards the chamber (as depicted in Figure 2(b)), which may explain the low spray cone angle obtained by RFM. For HRM, flash-boiling is more regular and seems less violent than for RFM. The liquid core is shorter with RFM which confirms its higher evaporation rate.

The higher vaporization rate in RFM results in an increased spray velocity, as shown in Figure 3, leading to a greater axial momentum. Additionally, the interaction between the liquid-phase jet and the nozzle wall causes a reduction in the spray cone angle, as evidenced by the mass fraction distribution in Figure 4. The half spray cone angle is computed as illustrated in Figure 4. The spray cone is obtained by adding the half spray cone angle on both sides. The spray cone angle for RFM is 15° while for HRM is 46° . This significant difference is due to the early (instantaneous) phase change leading to a shorter liquid core with RFM. The shape of the nozzle, and more specifically the length of the step, seems to play a crucial role in the behavior of the in-nozzle spray and, consequently, on the angle of the spray cone obtained.

Further, Figure 5 presents the temperature distribution near the nozzle exit, demonstrating the supe-

Figure 2. Density distribution at time $t = 300\mu s$ (a) HRM. (b) RFM. Red lines indicates the path of the thin liquid film on the step-walls.

Figure 3. Velocity distribution near nozzle exit at time $t = 300\mu s$ (a) HRM (b) RFM. The color contour represents the velocity magnitude.

priority of RFM in capturing the spray cooling effect associated with flash boiling. The RFM predicts a substantial temperature drop of $-100K$, compared to $-30K$ in the HRM, aligning more closely with experimental observations, which report a cooling range of approximately $-60K$.

2.3 Comparison with experiments

To evaluate the predictive accuracy of the numerical models, the simulated spray morphology is compared with experimental observations. A Diffuse Back Illumination image (DBI) (Figure 6) provides a visual representation of key spray characteristics, including jet breakup and its expansion near the nozzle exit. The spray cone angle at approximately $600\mu m$ from the nozzle exit reveals a value of $(52^\circ \pm 5^\circ)$ from the experiment. On the other hand, we obtained the spray cone angle as 46° from HRM, and 15° from RFM. The overall spray structure predicted by both HRM and RFM shows qualitative agreement with the experiment, as illustrated in Figure 4. The underprediction by RFM is primarily due to its assumption of thermodynamic equilibrium. This simplification restricts the model's ability to capture metastable phase, which are crucial for accurately simulating flash boiling atomization.

Conclusions

The present study shows a comparative analysis of HRM and RFM for flash boiling ammonia spray highlighting the key differences in their predictive capabilities. While HRM provides a reasonable estimation

Figure 4. Contour plot of total mass-fraction of ammonia NH_3 , i.e., (liquid+vapor) at time $t = 300\mu s$ (a) HRM (b) RFM.

Figure 5. Illustration of temperature distribution near nozzle exit at time $t = 300\mu s$ (a) HRM (b) RFM.

of the spray cone angle, it fails to capture the evaporative cooling effect observed in experiments. In contrast, RFM accurately predicts the spray cooling phenomenon. However, RFM underestimates the spray cone angle, which is attributed to its thermodynamic equilibrium assumption. Further advancements in RFM non-equilibrium modeling are required to improve its predictive accuracy. Key areas for future development include enhanced representation of nucleation site effects, and refining the thermodynamic model to better account for metastable region dynamics. These improvements will enhance the reliability of RFM-based flash boiling simulations.

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Figure 6. Diffuse Back Illumination (DBI) image of liquid ammonia spray in the steady injection stage, at approximately $t = 300\mu s$

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